

TITLE:

Evaluating quality of stroke acute care in European countries: a systematic review.

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ABSTRACT

Background: The attempt to evaluating hospitals quality encountered the flourishing support of the scientific literature and the growing interest of policy makers. Quality of health care is a multidimensional object and patients' population is heterogeneous for both clinical characteristics and socioeconomic status (SES). Yet, hospital factors may contribute to influence disease specific health outcomes. The purpose of this systematic review was to analyse the most common outcome indicators in assessing hospital quality and to explore which variables may have a significant impact on hospital quality evaluation. For this purpose, we narrowed the research to stroke acute treatment in European countries. Moreover, we screened and reported the publications data sources and the relative impact on the outcome evaluation.

Methods: We considered articles from PubMed and ECONPAPERS databases. The search strategy included the following topics: study characteristics, measures of quality outcomes, risk adjustment, case mix and hospital quality indicators. Both hospital and patient level risk adjustment were screened and analysed. Concerning the clinical literature, we restricted the research to stroke events.

Results: Overall, 36 studies from PubMed and 25 journal articles from ECONPAPERS were included in the analysis. Forty-one of them focused on stroke events. The most reported quality outcomes were readmission and mortality (in-hospital and after discharge). At patient level, the risk adjustment included six domains of variables: general patients' characteristics (100%), socio-economic (70%), clinical prognostic factors (55%), functionality (52,5%), comorbidities (77,5%) and severity at admission (45%). At hospital level, the most employed variables for the risk adjustment pertained to process of care and factors related to health technology provision (31/32). In particular, brain imaging, presence of a stroke unit care, clinical tests and length of stay resulted the most frequent variables. Nine studies (28%) included hospital ownership and further hospital variables.

Discussion: Hospital quality evaluation could either become an incentive to improving provider's performance, or a standardized tool for monitoring purposes in imperfect hospital markets. A comprehensive quality of care evaluation across hospitals requires the inclusion of a composite outcomes measurement and a multilevel adjustment. Overall, mortality within 30 days from discharge is the main outcome indicator employed for measuring hospital quality. At patient level, both clinical and sociodemographic characteristics were included in the risk adjustment. At hospital level, the majority of the studies selected miscellaneous factors, including process of care indicators and hospital market characteristics. Concerning the data source, administrative data clearly impose a limit to the inpatient information compared to clinical records; however, we did not find any large inconsistencies between the analysis based on administrative data and different sources.